

POLITICAL SCIENCES

CHINESE (SINICIZED) AND SOVIET MARXISM: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IDEATIONAL-THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND DOCTRINAL SOCIO-POLITICAL PRESCRIPTIONS OF THE PROJECTS OF SOCIALIST AND COMMUNIST CONSTRUCTION OF THE CPC AND THE CPSU

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277113>

Abstract

Based on the analysis of numerous publications from the second half of the nineteenth century and the first decades of the twentieth century by specialists in Soviet and Chinese Marxism, which have become two of its most influential paradigmatic varieties in the world, and metanarratives for the USSR and China, the article offers an innovative methodological approach for the scientific and heuristic study of the defining tendencies in the development of the Marxist philosophical and socio-political theory, its large-scale and institutionally supported attempts to adapt to the development conditions of a particular country. First of all, during the radical reform of the socialist economic and socio-political system already created in it.

The attributive features of modern Chinese Marxism (Marxism with Chinese specifics (the Chinese concept of "Adaptation of Marxism to the Chinese Context"), Sinicized Marxism), as the most effective version in world history for correcting and modernizing the axiomatics of the Marxist-Leninist theoretical model of social development, as well as improving the ideology of the ruling Communist Party in order to increase the effectiveness of its domestic and foreign state policies, have been characterized by means of concrete-historical and systematic comparative analysis of the ideational grounds and basic socio-philosophical postulates, political and ideological prescriptions of the program documents of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union and the Communist Party of China.

Within the framework of this study, special attention has been paid to highlighting the essence and features of the Soviet and Chinese strategy of socialist construction, created to implement Marxist socialist and communist projects, as well as revealing the scientific evaluation of the differences between the political doctrines of the CPSU and the CPC in the interpretation of objective logic (the duration of stages, goals, and objectives of fundamental economic, social, political, and cultural transformations) of the process of constructing high-level development socialism ("developed socialism") and the further progressive movement of such a society to the phase of communism.

Keywords: Marxism-Leninism, Chinese Marxism, Sinicized Marxism, Soviet Marxism, CPSU, CPC, developed socialism, communism

Introduction

In our opinion, it is first necessary to take into account and contrast its two most influential varieties, or theoretical models, which in socialist societies were also given the functions of metanarratives, in order to increase the effectiveness of analyzing the general trends and uniqueness of the processes of development

of Marxist teaching in the realities of Soviet-type political systems¹.

Such philosophical paradigms included Soviet Marxism (*Marxism-Leninism*) and Chinese (*Sinicized Marxism*)², which were also concurrent political and ideological doctrines.

¹ As you are aware, *metanarrative* is not the only valid theoretical model, teaching, or paradigm accepted by the majority of scientists. It is a *conception* or *theory* on the one hand that "claims universality, cultural dominance, and legitimizes" knowledge, various social institutions, and a particular way of thinking, and it is *ideology* on the other hand that "imposes on society and culture as a whole a certain ideological complex of ideas," "limiting, suppressing, ordering, and controlling" social life, and "committing violence against a person, his consciousness" (Korotchenko, 2001, p. 459). By the way, the "irony" of dialectics in the movement of world history, as evidenced by a large number of publications, including those by Western scientists, publicists, and political and economic experts, turned out to be that something

symptomatic and similar happened at the end of the 20th century – at the beginning of the 21st century with *liberalism* (as a symbiosis of political ideology, philosophy, and ideological values, as well as the postulates of economic theory). Its most striking manifesto was the program work of **Francis Fukuyama**, "The End of History?", first published in the United States in 1989 and then translated from English into many languages around the world.

² It is important to note that, in contrast to its Russian-language version of the Constitution of the Communist Party of China (see, Full Text of the CPC Constitution, 2017) and works by Chinese authors published in the Russian Federation (see, for example, Li Junju, 2017), in the *CPC Program's English translation*

According to our estimates, this type of Marxism can be considered the result of the realization of the philosophical, theoretical, and political-ideological conviction of **Mao Zedong**, who, as early as October 1938, at the Sixth Plenum of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China's Sixth Convocation, proclaimed, "*There is no such thing as abstract Marxism; there is only concrete Marxism*" (cited by Li Junju, 2017).

In light of the foregoing, it stands to reason that the Chinese researcher **Zhang Shuhua**, having evaluated and assessed **Lenin's** innovations, in particular, V.I. Lenin's radical renewal of the theory of proletarian revolution and socialist construction, developed by the founders of Marxism, and using the theoretical postulate of I.V. Stalin (formulated by him in the lecture "On the Foundations of Leninism" in 1924, which was then published in all editions of his collections "Questions of Leninism," as well as The Collected Works), which emphasizes that "*Leninism is Marxism of the era of imperialism and proletarian revolution*", made a rather radical conclusion. He stated that *Leninism* is a new "stage of manifestation of the concrete practice of Marxism in Russia", which means that it is nothing more than "*Russified Marxism*" (Zhang Shuhua, 2017).

Therefore, it appears that the scientist from the People's Republic of China has clarified the meanings of **Mao Zedong** concept of "*sinicized Marxism*" and revealed the logic of its development and introduction into scientific and ideological discourses, while also offering its theoretical justification for both Marxists and anti-Marxists. However, in our opinion, if we are to defend our concept based on Stalin's theories, then in order to understand the modern stage of China's development, as well as the role of the CCP and the state governed by it, it is necessary to include the definition of Leninism that **I.V. Stalin** used to end his lecture. And it says, "The essence of Leninism in the party and state work lies in the combination of Russian revolutionary scope with American efficiency" (Stalin, 1952, p. 118).

Here, we should also mention that **Yu.V. Andropov**, general secretary of the CPSU Central Committee, could have the potential to oppose of **Zhang Shuhua** interpretation of *Leninism as merely "Russified Marxism"*. In the article "The Teachings of **Karl Marx** and the Problems of Socialist Construction in the USSR" (1983), that is, in the policy document for the Soviet Communist Party (which, of course, was prepared by a large team of leading social theorists and party ideological hierarchs of the Soviet Union), not only did he unequivocally state that "Leninism was the Marxism of the era of imperialism and proletarian revolutions, the collapse of the colonial system, the era of the transition of humanity from capitalism to socialism", but also make the following important theoretical conclusion: "*Outside of Leninism, Marxism is simply*

impossible in our time". (Andropov, 1983, p. 7). In general, the sense-postulate of **Andropov** was limited to the fact that *Leninism* was not some special, national, and even more so, Russified type of Marxist theory and the party political and ideological doctrine, but the only possible form of Marxism in the modern era of radical social transformations. All this, of course, presupposes both its further development and ideological and theoretical enrichment on the basis of the scientific study of the essence and specifics of new Marxist models of socialist construction under the conditions of the fundamental transformation of the modern world system in the 21st century.

In addition, it should be noted that for the scientific and heuristic study of Chinese Marxism, an adequate assessment of the possibilities, goals, and prospects for its renewal in accordance with the conditions of the modern world, a theoretical understanding of the positive achievements and mistakes of Soviet philosophers and social scientists (see, for resample, Vilkov, 2021, p. 116-139), which became obvious as a result of their numerous attempts to modernize Marxism-Leninism (*Russified Marxism*) and the Soviet Communist Party political and ideological doctrine after the death of I.V. Stalin and before the collapse of the USSR, becomes of great importance³.

1. Specifics of the Research Methodology of Modern Chinese Marxism

In order to understand the specifics of modern Marxism in the PRC it is, first of all, necessary to consider that Marxism-Leninism is declared in the CCP Program as the basic component of its Constitution (adopted by the 19th National Congress of the CCP in 2017) as one of the ideological and theoretical foundations of the activities of Chinese communists. In this regard (taking into account the CPC's decisive role in the life of Chinese society and the entire state, its program documents), several extremely important and fundamental statutory provisions should be adopted as an analytical setting and coordinate system, which actually serve as ideological-theoretical and political-philosophical constants, respectively – research prescriptions.

It is necessary to further concretize the general belief that was previously suggested. First, regarding the research methodology; and second, regarding its object and subject. And most importantly, scientific standards dictate that the optimal analytical model should be built on the principle of compliance of cognition methods with the phenomenon or process that has become the object of cognitive activity.

If we assess the methodological component of the theoretical understanding of the specifics of philosophical axiomatics, socio-political and ideological attitudes, which in their integrity characterize the attribu-

the terms "*Sinicized Marxism*" or "*Sinicization of Marxism*" does not use (see, Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017). *The following construct is used instead: "adaptation of Marxism to the Chinese context"*.

³ More specifically, the distribution of the territory, production, and resource base between the high-

est republican and union party, managerial, and economic nomenclature, which held complete political, economic, ideological (spiritual), and administrative power in the Soviet Union, rather than the collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics.

tive features of Marxism institutionalized in the People's Republic of China, then, in our opinion, such traditional methods of historical and philosophical research as description, author's interpretation, comments, purely factual or, conversely, abstract-reflective philosophical way of understanding the material (which mainly makes up the content of publications by specialists in Chinese Marxism) will not help to obtain a systemic and fundamental vision of the essence of that version of Marxist theory which was formed and became dominant in the PRC. And, as long-term scientific research practice has demonstrated, the use of such methods (which are typically empirical in their epistemological capabilities) can effectively ensure the creation of a more or less accurate, complete, or, conversely, fragmentary picture of only points of view on Chinese Marxism, as well as contribute to the highlighting and systematization of existing interpretations and theoretical reconstructions of the genesis, structure, various functions, etc., of the Marxist theory and political doctrine of the CCP in China

Therefore, according to our estimates, the analytical model for understanding the history, essence, specifics, and contradictory practice of implementing the Marxist teaching in the PRC requires a methodology based on a set of principles and attitudes of the dialectical approach.

It has traditionally been recognized as the only correct scientific methodological foundation of Marxism itself, its universal and common method of scientific cognition of any phenomena and processes in the world (natural, social, spiritual, etc.), and now it has become a methodological platform, a methodological tool for such an influential field of cognition of socio-historical and political-ideological processes, known as "*historical politology*⁴ (i.e., *political science*)".

In terms of the specifics of the object and subject of research (i.e., Chinese or Sinicized Marxism), *historical politology* methodology allows for both concrete historical and general and political-philosophical comparative analysis. Moreover, the analysis, on the one hand, of the version of Marxist teaching, the model and logic of socialist and communist construction, which are declared in the main documents of the Chinese Communist Party, the works of its leaders, and, on the other hand, the theoretical coverage of the classical

postulates of Marxism-Leninism and the doctrinal, program socio-political, and political-ideological attitudes of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (under the leadership of **M.S. Khrushchev**, who came to power in the CPSU and the USSR, began an ideological and political confrontation with the Communist Party of China). In short, on the methodological platform of historical *politology*, effective understanding and adequate coverage of the attributive features of Chinese Marxism as a philosophical theory and ideological foundation of the doctrine and strategy of the ruling party in the PRC are possible only by comparing the common and distinctive features between Chinese and Soviet Marxism (Marxism-Leninism). And at the moment, the provisions and attitudes of the general program of the CPC (included in its 2017 Constitution) and then partially reproduced in the latest version of the Constitution of the People's Republic of China in 2018, should be recognized as the theoretical and ideological quintessence of the first of them. Because in addition to a concentrated description of the essence of modern metanarrative (metaparadigm) Marxist social science theory in the PRC, the fundamental conceptual and unambiguous political and ideological assessments of the present and future status of socialist China have been clearly formulated in the CPC Program (as an integral system and through a purely symbolic link to the two most significant dates and historical events for the Chinese people and their political leadership – their "centenary anniversaries" of 2019 and 2049), and the prospects and directions of its development for the upcoming decades are clearly defined.

2. The Main Provisions of the General Program of the Communist Party of China as a System of Ideational-Theoretical and Political-Ideological Foundations of the Analysis of Modern Chinese (Sinicized) Marxism

So, the first (*philosophical, socio-political, and political-ideological foundations of modern Chinese, that is, Sinicized Marxism*) goes as follows: "*The Communist Party of China uses Marxism-Leninism*", but creatively supplements it with "*Mao Zedong Thought, Deng Xiaoping Theory, the Theory of Three Represents, the Scientific Outlook on Development, and*

⁴ The term "*politology*" is used here. In the scientific categorical apparatus of many Slavic-speaking nations, it predominates over other terms to refer to the body of scientific disciplines and knowledge collectively referred to as "political science/sciences" in the Anglo-American tradition. In the latter case, there are pros and cons. On the one hand, numerous distinct directions and approaches have been formed as a result of the study of political phenomena and processes. And although they have a common object of knowledge, i.e., the political sphere of public life, each of them has its own special subject of research (for example, the history of political thought, political institutions, etc.). Therefore, all of these various fields of political knowledge can be formally unified under the term "political science." On the other hand, it is wrong to consider political studies "science," since the main task and result of scientific knowledge and theoretical modeling of existing reality

(the best example of which is classical Newtonian mechanics) is to discover and formulate laws. However, centuries-old political studies have not yet produced such a result, i.e., they have not formulated any laws or regularities (they mean stable, repetitive cause-and-effect relationships that are probabilistic in nature). In political science, three regularities that **Maurice Duverger** fixed and conceptualized are frequently recognized as laws. They explain the most stable and typical tendencies in the functioning of electoral systems under democratic political regimes. Meanwhile, **Duverger** considered the found and generalized regularities to be sociological rather than political in nature. Or, in other words, those electoral processes that the French sociologist discovered and explained as tendencies-regularities were not theoretical achievements of political science/sciences but rather of a discipline known as "sociology of politics."

Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era as its guides to action". At the same time, the General Program emphasizes: "With Comrade **Mao Zedong** as their chief representative, Chinese Communists developed *Mao Zedong Thought* by combining the basic tenets of Marxism-Leninism with the actual practice of the Chinese revolution. *Mao Zedong Thought* is the application and development of Marxism-Leninism in China; it is a body of theoretical principles and a summary of experiences, proven correct in practice, relating to China's revolution and construction; and it is a crystallization of the collective wisdom of the Communist Party of China" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 1).

In addition to the above, as a theoretical program, the Constitution of the CPC includes an additional explanation of the relationship of **Marx** and **Lenin's** teaching with the innovative conceptions of its former and current leaders. They also fix the semantic framework of the concept of "Sinicization of Marxism". "*Xi Jinping Thought on Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era*", written in the Program provisions of the Constitution of the Communist Party of China, "is a continuation and development of *Marxism-Leninism, Mao Zedong Thought, Deng Xiaoping Theory, the Theory of Three Represents* (formulated in **Jiang Zemin's** report, November 2002 – V. V.), and the *Scientific Outlook on Development* (presented by **Hu Jintao** at the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, November 2012 – V. V.). It is the latest achievement in adapting Marxism to the Chinese context, a crystallization of the practical experience and collective wisdom of the Party and the people, an important component of the theoretical system of socialism with Chinese characteristics, and a guide to action for the entire Party and all the Chinese people to strive for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, and must be upheld long term and constantly developed" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 2-3).

The second program provision (milestone stages and fundamental socio-economic, political, spiritual, and cultural transformations in China during the time of Mao's state and political leadership) states: "Under the guidance of **Mao Zedong Thought**, the Communist Party of China led the Chinese people of all ethnic groups ... securing victory in the new democratic revolution and founding the People's Republic of China, a people's democratic dictatorship⁵. After the founding of the People's Republic, the Communist Party of

China successfully led the people in carrying out socialist transformation, completing the transition from New Democracy to socialism, establishing the basic socialist system, and developing a socialist economy, politics, and culture" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 1).

Third provision (factors and large-scale achievements of the CPC in the socialist construction as a result of its policy based on Deng Xiaoping theory):

a) "**Deng Xiaoping Theory** is the product of combining Marxism-Leninism's basic tenets with practice in contemporary China and the particular features of the era; it is a continuation and development of **Mao Zedong Thought** under new historical conditions; it represents a new stage for the development of Marxism in China; it is the Marxism of contemporary China and a crystallization of the collective wisdom of the Communist Party of China; and it guides the continuous progression of China's socialist modernization";

b) "Ultimately, the fundamental reason for all of China's achievements and progress since reform and opening up began is that the Party has forged a path, formed a theoretical system, established a system, and developed a culture for socialism with Chinese characteristics" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 2-3).

The fourth system provision (party ideological and theoretical postulates and ideological prescriptions, necessary prerequisites and conditions, as well as driving forces for ensuring progress in the socialist development of the PRC): "All Party members must cherish deeply, uphold long-term, and continue to develop this path (further development of socialism with Chinese specifics, characteristics. – V. V.), this theoretical system (Sinicized Marxism. – V. V.), this socialist system, and this culture, which the Party has developed through great hardship". All members of CPC "must hold high the great banner of socialism with Chinese characteristics, have firm confidence in its path, theory, system, and culture, implement the Party's basic theory, basic line, and basic policy, and strive to fulfill the three historic tasks of advancing modernization, achieving China's reunification, and safeguarding world peace and promoting common development, achieve the two (2021 and 2049 – V. V.) centenary goals, and realize the Chinese Dream of national rejuvenation and the Chinese Dream of national rejuvenation" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 3).

However, in our opinion, it is problematic to consider the newest program idea of the CPC, "*the Chinese*

⁵ It is important to note that Lenin's conception, both prior to and following 1917, affirmed and justified the absolute necessity of establishing the "dictatorship of the proletariat". According to Lenin, his associates in the RSDLP (b), associates, and followers in the USSR, the dictatorship of the proletariat is the highest form of democracy. Without it, the victory of the socialist revolution and the provision of socialist construction is impossible. The official document of the CPSU – its third program – adopted at the XXII Congress in 1961 clearly and imperatively formulates the idea that only the "dictatorship of the proletariat", and not any other social-class group or community, can ensure the victory of the

socialist revolution and the construction of a socialist system in any country. "*The experience of the USSR*", declared in the program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, "proved that people can come to socialism only as a result of the socialist revolution and the implementation of the dictatorship of the proletariat. This experience fully confirmed the principles of the socialist revolution and socialist construction, which are of general importance, despite some peculiarities, caused by specific historical conditions of the construction of socialism in the Soviet Union in the conditions of a hostile capitalist environment" (Program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 1965, p. 509).

Dream of national rejuvenation" (in the Russian translation of the General Program of the CPC – "*the great revival of the Chinese nation*") to be ideologically natural for China, especially for socialist China, where the Communist Party has been in power for decades and its political doctrine was proclaimed Marxist and still remains so. Although theorists and ideologists in the PRC (since Mao Zedong) constantly emphasize that Chinese Marxism has a special uniqueness, it objectively and historically has a pronounced specificity, which has even received (primarily outside the Chinese philosophical and social studies discourse) its own name: "*Sinicized Marxism*" or, in terms of party documents, "*adaptation of Marxism to the Chinese context*" (see, for example, Vilkov, 2022, pp. 70-82).

And to understand what has been said about the idea of "*national rejuvenation*" (as the central idea, the quintessence of the socio-philosophical concept, as well as the political ideologeme and mythologeme), it is important to remember that in its genesis it was, first of all, purely *European*, and secondly, according to its socio-political and ideological essence and purpose, *non-Marxist*. Such an ideologeme, with a variety of forms and methods of its own philosophical justification and political popularization ("implantation in the mass consciousness"), was created for the conditions of formation and intensive capitalist development of society (according to the terminology of the second half of the twentieth century – market economy); for its bourgeois-democratic economic, institutional, political, and socio-cultural transformations (revolutionary or evolutionary); and does not correspond at all to the realities, processes, and goals of socialist construction at any of its stages and in any of its spheres. It includes a multi-dimensional national component of the existence of society as a community or group of people, consolidated (stable and relatively separated from other nation-state entities) by economic ties, unity of the ethnic territory, common language, culture, self-awareness, traditions, and mentality.

In the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, "the idea of national rejuvenation" served a variety of socio-political, spiritual, and cultural purposes in the ethno-political mobilization of the population. First and foremost, it provided one of the two – but still the only one, by political standards and values – variants of the objective logic of the global process of national and nation-state building or creation.

The first of them was the "*Western European*" path of civilizational development, as numerous reputable researchers have now demonstrated (classic examples of which are France and the United States, where the movement "*from state to nation*" became the defining trend where, for the most part, the nation is not an ethnic community or an ethno-cultural kinship but a community of civil or, in other modern terms, a political community under a democratic political regime).

Its alternative was the *central and Eastern European way of consolidating the people-nation and creating a sovereign national state for it*, based on and thanks to the active use of the ideologeme and mythologeme of "national rejuvenation" (first in Germany and Italy in the nineteenth century and then a clear renaissance (according to the terminology of **Habermas** – "*the fourth wave of nationalization*") occurred in history in the late 1980s and early 1990s during the "collapse of the USSR" and disappearance of the "socialist commonwealth" system in Eastern Europe). From a logical standpoint, this process was a deliberate, democratically approved movement that was coordinated and encouraged by political and cultural elites using the "*from nation to state*" model. Ideally, a state of one nation, which would be nationally and ethnically unified, with no significant linguistic, cultural, or mental differentiation among its citizens. "Here", notes the world-famous philosopher **Jü. Habermas**, "the formation of the nation state followed the propaganda spread of the national consciousness that preceded it" (Habermas, 2001, p. 197). "Nation-building" was preceded by "state-building", and the primary stage of nation-building was the mental constitution of the nation. And for this reason, a number of events were held to create the impression of a spiritually and culturally established "nation of the people" that had existed for many centuries or even millennia. The movement to establish a single ethnocultural "self-identification" and kinship, which was motivated by "intellectuals", was the dominant sociopolitical force in this process. Initially, the "nation of the people" received life in the works of philosophers, historians, writers, and journalists, who "paved the path for the diplomatic and military efforts of statesmen," "bringing to the masses an imaginary project of a nation united on the cultural basis" (Habermas, 2002, p. 367)⁶.

In general, in the context of the above-mentioned information, the attempts of Chinese theorists and ideologists to doctrinally apply both the concept and ideologeme, as well as the concept of "*national rejuvenation*," in some historical cases objectively and without alternative, necessary for national state-political independence, and specifically fill the content of the concepts of "*people*" and "*nation*," can be recognized as a *significant theoretical deviation from Marxism* (the one that was developed by its founders, and especially from the Soviet one). As evidenced by examples of the use of these scientific, political and ideological terms in the CPC program documents (in particular, in the structure of key constructs/ideas, such as "*The People's Republic Of China – Democratic dictatorship of the people*"; "the Chinese dream of the *great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation*"; "*The basic line of the Communist Party of China in the primary stage of socialism is to lead and unite the people of all ethnic groups...*", etc.), their meanings-senses are more pertained not to Marxism,

⁶ To find a detailed analysis of the method and global trend of the nation- and state-building described succinctly above, see, in particular: Vilkov, 2014, p. 91-185; Vilkov, 2017, p. 5-16; Vilkov, V. 2018a, p. 10-28; Vilkov, 2017a, p. 101-119, 328-354; Rudenko,

Vilkov, 2020, p. 86-101; Rudenko, Vilkov, 2020a, p. 167-192; Vilkov, 2021a, p. 140-151; Vilkova, 2020, p. 37-64.

but to the *Eastern European* pre-Marxist and non-Marxist scientific and intellectual or socio-political and philosophical traditions. It was founded and popularized by the works of prominent philosophers, historians, writers, legal scholars, linguists, and social psychologists (the school of "psychology of peoples") in the late 18th – early 20th centuries (the most influential figures, ideological founders – **W. Wundt, J. Herder, G. Hegel, V. Humboldt, J. Grimm, G. Mazzini, M. Lazarus, G. Le Bon, P. Mancini, J. De Mestre, A. Muller, F. Novalis, G. Puchta, F. Savigny, L. Tieck, F. Schelling, F. Schlegel, F. Schleiermacher, H. Steinthal, J. Fichte, A. Fullier** and many others), and then became dominant in scientific and political-ideological discourses, as well as in the categorical apparatus of non-Marxist theories of the nation, widespread in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe. It is in the meaning of the hypotheses and axioms of this intellectual and scientific tradition and the variant of modeling the world-historical process of national genesis and state-political development that ethno-cultural and political-legal synonymization, the interweaving of the connotations of the concepts of "people" and "nation", took place. In order to describe this phenomenon as both an ethno-cultural reality and primarily as a scientific, political-philosophical, ideological, and mental construct, **Jü. Habermas** proposed the concept of the "nation of the people" (Volknation). Fundamentally, this kind of nation is not reliant on the state as a source of political authority and can exist for a very long time both with and without it. According to the concept of this German philosopher, an almost alternative socio-political and cultural-ethnic phenomenon is the "nation of state citizens" (Staatsnation). Or, according to the terms of another German researcher, **Egbert Jahn**, such a purely *political* or *civil nation* in the conditions of the democratic system of Western countries can be called a "nation-state", since it is a "nation-bearer of the state" and "most often is a titular one" (Yan, 2000, p. 116).

Therefore, the inclusion of the non-Marxist ideologue and mythologeme of "national rejuvenation" (for example, the wording "*realization of the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation*" or "*promote a national spirit*" and, in particular, the assertion in the General Program of the Communist Party of China that the theoretical Marxist developments of its leaders, from Mao Zedong to Xi Jinping, are "the latest achievement in adapting Marxism to the Chinese context (in the Russian translation CPC's General Program – "*Sinicization of Marxism*"), a crystallization of the practical experience and collective wisdom of the

Party and the people", and serve as "a guide to action for the entire Party and all the Chinese people to strive for the *great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation*") in the Marxist political and philosophical theory/discourse, the political program and the ideological doctrine of the CPC should, in our opinion, be viewed as another systemic, *symbolic, semantic and lexical* construction. It conceals, figuratively and literally, the very real and global strategic goals and objectives of the current Chinese Communist Party and state leadership. In essence, they aim to significantly improve the PRC's status in the political and economic structures of the world. In the first case, China's economy was transformed into the top economy in the world in terms of GDP (gross domestic product) and per capita income, as well as attaining a level of economic development that would guarantee China's complete economic domination in the twenty-first century. That is, the acquisition of such an economic role, but already in a new, emerging world system and technological order, comparable in scale and influence to the one that China played for many centuries a little more than two centuries ago (until the middle of the eighteenth century), when it significantly outperformed all Western countries in terms of domestic production and foreign trade. In the second, in state-political terms, the idea of the "great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation" includes the requirement to "complete" the "*great cause of the unification of the Motherland*" or "*reunification of the Motherland*", i.e., the return of the "sacred territory of China" – Taiwan, several islands belonging to it (i.e., the remainder of the state of the Republic of China⁷), and also the adjacent waters of the South China Sea and straits, under the sovereign authority, under state-political, military control and the exclusive jurisdiction of the People's Republic of China.

Characterizing the program provisions of the Program of the CPC as theoretical-methodological and political-ideological foundations and conceptual coordinates of the analysis of the official version of Sinicized Marxism, it should also be taken into account, that based on the axiomatics of Marxist dialectics, which asserts and proves that the source and driving force of any development process are primarily internal antagonistic and non-antagonistic contradictions in the social system, and their solution naturally leads it to a new, usually more progressive state, the Chinese communists consider the following as the basic contradiction in modern socialist China: "*At the present stage, the principal contradiction in Chinese society is that between the ever-growing needs of the people for a better life*

⁷ The Republic of China was established in 1912 on the territory of mainland China and the islands belonging to it at that time (as well as parts of the territory of Mongolia) under the leadership of the National Kuomintang Party. After losing power in mainland China as a result of Japanese aggression and occupation (1937–1945), the establishment of the PRC in 1949, and defeat in the civil war of 1945–1950 by the People's Liberation Army of China (led by the CCP), the Republic of China and Kuomintang retained power in Taiwan (after WW II, Japan ceded control of this island, as well as

the Penghu archipelago and a number of smaller islands, to the Republic of China). Being the formal heir, the receiver of the all-Chinese state power, and then an independent state entity (now it has diplomatic relations with only 13 countries), the Republic of China (Taiwan) became the founder of the UN and one of the five permanent members of the Security Council. In 1971, as a result, first of all, of a radical improvement in the relations of the state and political leadership of the PRC with the United States and, conversely, their deterioration with the USSR, Taiwan (the Republic of China) took the place of the PRC in the UN Security Council.

and unbalanced and inadequate development" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 3).

By the way, the CCP Program refers to **Mao's** ideas about the fundamental difference between "two types of contradictions that are not the same in nature", on the one hand, "within the people" (first of all, these are socio-class, ideological, and worldview contradictions between the "people" and the "national bourgeoisie"), and on the other hand, irreconcilable contradictions between the people and their "enemies". This classification was developed and characterized by Mao in a speech delivered by him on February 27, 1957, at the 11th expanded session of the Supreme State Conference (respectively, then published not only in China but also in the USSR). And to solve them, the "Great Helmsman" suggested using, depending on the situation and the severity of the conflict of interests, democratic and undemocratic (violent) methods, approaches, and means (see, for example, Mao Zedong, 1957, pp. 3-22). The same contradictions made by **Mao Zedong** and their typology are stated as follows in the current Program: "The Party shall strengthen and develop new approaches to social governance. *It shall strictly distinguish between and properly handle contradictions between us and enemies and contradictions among the people, these two different types of contradiction. It shall strengthen comprehensive measures to maintain law and order*, and work with firm resolve and in accordance with the law to combat criminal activities that endanger national security and national interests, or threaten social stability or economic development, and will bring criminals to justice, maintaining lasting social stability". In addition, the Communist Party of China "shall pursue a holistic approach to national security and resolutely safeguard China's sovereignty, security, and development interests" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 6).

One particular statutory requirement can be identified among the contemporary inventions regarding the enemies of the Chinese people: "*Throughout the whole course of socialist modernization, the Party must ... oppose bourgeois liberalization*" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 4).

Fifth statutory provision (*prospects and timeframes for the PRC's improvement, as well as the country's current socioeconomic status and level of formation development*). "China – it is written in the CCP Program – *is currently in the primary stage of socialism and will remain so for a long time to come. This is a stage of history that cannot be bypassed as China, which used to be economically and culturally lagging, makes progress in socialist modernization; it will take over a century*. China's development of socialism must begin from China's own circumstances and must follow the path of socialism with Chinese characteristics. ... *In this new era in the new century, the strategic objectives of economic and social development are to finish building a moderately prosperous society in all respects by the time the Party marks its centenary (2021, – V.V.) and to build China into a great modern socialist country in every dimension by the time the People's*

Republic celebrates its centenary (2049, – V.V.)" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 3-4).

3. Doctrinal Prescriptions of the CPSU and CPC Projects of Socialist and Communist Construction

The main programmatic socio-political postulate of the current Constitution of the CPC (the key ideas and prescriptions of the "strategic vision for the development of socialism with Chinese characteristics", directives for the CCP's efforts at the current stage of socialist construction) proclaims: "*The basic line of the Communist Party of China in the primary stage of socialism, the statutory requirement proclaims, is to lead all the people of China together in a self-reliant and pioneering effort, making economic development the central task, upholding the Four Cardinal Principles, and remaining committed to reform and opening up, so as to see China becomes a great modern socialist country that is prosperous, strong, democratic, culturally advanced, harmonious, and beautiful*". In addition, according to the main document of the Chinese communists: "*Only through reform and opening up can we develop China, develop socialism, and develop Marxism*" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, pp. 4-5).

And finally, *it is time to talk about the communist future of the Chinese people and the objective prerequisites for building a communist society in China*. This following statutory provision of the CPC is of great importance for the study of Chinese (Sinicized) Marxism and is necessary for understanding the strategic goal of socio-political transformations in the current PRC (its fundamental difference, on the one hand, from the ideology-mythology that accelerated – in less than 20 years – the construction of communism in the USSR, proclaimed by **M.S. Khrushchev** at the XXII Congress of the CPSU in October 1961 and declared in its new (third) Program, and on the other hand, the obvious analogy with the Soviet concept and party doctrine of "developed socialism" as a natural transitional stage (phase, period) of building a communist society, proclaimed in the "Brezhnev era of stagnation"). It states: "*The Party's highest ideal and ultimate goal is the realization of communism. ... Marxism-Leninism reveals the laws governing the development of the history of human society. Its basic tenets are correct and have tremendous vitality. The highest ideal of communism pursued by Chinese Communists can be realized only when socialist society is fully developed and highly advanced*".

Particular emphasis was placed on the following: "*The development and improvement of the socialist system is a long historical process. By upholding the basic tenets of Marxism-Leninism and following the path suited to China's specific conditions as chosen by the Chinese people, China's socialist cause will ultimately be victorious*" (Constitution of the Communist Party of China, 2017, p. 1).

Thus, from the provision cited above, it becomes quite obvious that *in the Sinicized variant of Marxism*, just as in the party doctrine of the CPC, the main goal

of any true supporter of communist beliefs is to build communism. It is proclaimed by Chinese Marxist Communists as the highest ideal and the sole strategic objective that dictates the course of their nation's continued, forward-moving development. However, it should be noted that neither in the Chinese Marxist social and political-philosophical theory nor in the scientific discourse nor in the program documents of the CPC is the concept of "*scientific communism*" used (and in Chinese social studies it is not even discussed, especially not developed theoretically), as it was in the USSR after 1961 and before the disappearance of the Soviet Union in 1991.

It is important to stress that the latter (socio-political theory in the USSR) underwent a radical theoretical and ideological reform, especially to serve the propaganda objectives and interests of the post-Stalin communist party leadership. Its essence and consequences lay in the fact that *in the Soviet social science and political and ideological discourses after the XXII Congress of the CPSU (1961), Lenin's notion of "scientific socialism"*⁸ in relation to Marxism *was adjusted to the connotation of the concept of "scientific communism", which actually replaced it. And since then, it has become general and basic in the Soviet Marxist-Leninist theory of social development and the political and ideological doctrine of the CPSU.*

In order to provide a scientific assessment of the political history of the USSR, it is important to recall that the ideologeme and theoretical concept of "scientific communism" started to be actively used and promoted in the official program documents of the CPSU, in the speeches of its leaders, and during the Khrushchev, post-Stalin and anti-Stalin epochs. For example, in the Resolution of the Extraordinary XXI Congress of the CPSU (from January 27 to February 5, 1959), it was stated: "The strength of the Communist Party lies in its loyalty to Marxism-Leninism, in the creative application and development of the theory of scientific communism" (From the Resolution of the XXI Congress of the Communist Party..., 1965, p. 421). In his address to the XXII Congress of the Soviet Communist Party (1961), which traditionally served as a report of the CPSU central committee, First Secretary of the Soviet Communist Party, **N.S. Khrushchev**, used a similar formulation. "Our party's strength resides in the fact that it has been able to unite in its revolutionary and transformative actions the theory and practice of scientific communism," Khrushchev said in it (*Report of the Central Committee of the Communist Party ... Report of Comrade N.S. Khrushchev*, 1962, p. 125). And, for example, in the new Program of the party adopted by the XXII Congress of the CPSU, it was stated that the party was publicly called "**the party of scientific communism**" (Program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 1965, p. 546).

Additionally, since the end of the 1950s, "*the founders of Marxism*" (after **Stalin**, these were thought to be only **Karl Marx**, **Friedrich Engels** and **Vladimir**

I. Lenin in the Soviet philosophical and sociological communities and, above all, in the political and ideological discourse) have also started to be called the "creators of scientific communism" in party publications and speeches by the Communist Party of the USSR leaders. Though it is important to note that neither in their political and ideological teachings nor in their social and philosophical analysis, the classics of Marxism themselves did not use the concept of "*scientific communism*".

From an ideological standpoint, the development of the concept known as "scientific communism" (in Soviet social studies and subsequent active development by social scientists, including its deployment into a holistic theory that served as the main ideological foundation for the USSR Communist Party's doctrine and strategic plan) is entirely logical. *First*, it was another declaration that the doctrine of **Marx**, **Engels** and **Lenin** about communism is not a utopia, unlike all pre-Marxist conceptually formed ideas about socialist and communist society. *Second*, this was a peculiar public statement by the Soviet party and ideological hierarchs to the Soviet people and the whole world that in the USSR Stalin's stage of building socialism was "mostly" completed and the next natural stage of development of the communist socio-economic formation – the construction of the socio-economic and spiritual-cultural foundation of communism – had begun. According to the theory of **K. Marx**, **F. Engels**, and **V.I. Lenin**, and later with Soviet Marxism, it was an integral formation that naturally passed through the *two phases* of its progress: "*socialist*" and "*communist*". *Thirdly*, because Marxist-Leninist philosophy has always positioned itself as "ideological science and scientific ideology", the use of the concept of "scientific communism" did not allow any doubt that the process of creating a communist society in the USSR would be based not on the fantasies or dreams of communists, and above all on the leadership of the CPSU of the Khrushchev era, but solely on the basis of scientific knowledge about society, on the objective laws of its entire history known and scientifically understood by Marxists.

Here, it is worth reminding ourselves that the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the CPSU, **N.S. Khrushchev**, in his report "On the Program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union", declared: "The main result of the activities of the Party and the people is a complete and final victory of socialism in the USSR". Being the sovereign head of not only the Soviet state but also the Marxist party (CPSU), **Khrushchev**, in a report to the Congress, categorically stated: "The draft program marks a *new stage in the development of Marx, Engels, and Lenin's revolutionary theory*"; it "represents the philosophical, economic, and political basis for the construction of communism in our country"; and its main advantage is that "*this is a specific, scientifically based communism construction program*". Explaining in more detail his position on the allegedly exclusively scientific and theoretically substan-

⁸ Let us give a convincing example of Lenin's work of 1909, "On the Attitude of the Workers' Party to Religion." In it, **V.I. Lenin** emphasizes, "*Social democracy*

(including Lenin's party, the RSDLP (b) – V.V.) *builds its worldview on the basis of scientific socialism, that is, Marxism*" (Lenin, 1980, p. 415).

tiated terms for the implementation of the party program, respectively, and communist construction in the Soviet Union, the First Secretary of the CPSU Central Committee stated: "The historical framework of the draft program is 20 years. Why did we stop at these particular time frames? Was there too much time allotted for this task during the discussion of the draft program, several friends questioned? No, comrades. ... We are guided strictly by scientific calculations. And calculations show that in 20 years we will build a predominantly communist society" (On the Program of the Communist Party... Report of the Comrade N.S. Khrushchev, 1962, pp. 151,162,166-167).

In the program adopted by the delegates of the XXII Congress of the CPSU (although, to many Marxist theorists and politicians, as well as hundreds of millions of people, its strategic objectives and declared deadlines for implementation seemed not only a utopia, but a complete absurdity), the stages of communist construction were clearly defined: "*In the coming decade* (1961–1970), the Soviet Union, creating the material and technical base of Communism, will surpass the most powerful and rich country of capitalism – the United States – in terms of production per capita; material well-being and the cultural and technical level of workers will significantly increase; everyone will be provided with material prosperity; all collective farms and state farms will turn into high-yielding and high-income farms; basically, the needs of Soviet people in well-maintained homes will be met; hard physical labor will disappear; the USSR will become the country with the shortest working day.

As a result of the second decade (1971–1980), a material and technical base of Communism will be created, providing an invention of material and cultural goods for the entire population; the Soviet society will closely approach the implementation of the principle of distribution according to needs, and there will be a gradual transition to one communal property. Thus, the USSR will predominantly become a communist society. The construction of a communist society will be fully completed in the following period" (Program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 1965, pp. 546-54).

From the point of view of Marxist theory, that is, Soviet Marxism-Leninism and the party doctrine of the CPSU of the late 1950s and early 1960s, no additional, necessary (economically, socially, politically, etc.) transitional stage between the phases of socialism and communism, which soon became known as "*developed socialism*", was expected. Its theoretical justification was developed in the scientific literature and declared

in the program documents of the CPSU and the Constitution of the USSR in the "era of Brezhnev", who took the highest party and state posts after the forced resignation of **N.S. Khrushchev**, who was sent into retirement at his own request. But in fact, he lost power as a result of a conspiracy of his "loyal associates" in the Politburo of the Central Committee, including **L.I. Brezhnev**.

It should also be noted that in the aforementioned report by **N.S. Khrushchov**, it was stated regarding the relationship between the stages of socialism and communism that "the classics of Marxism-Leninism emphasized that communism is not fenced off by a wall from socialism; these are two phases of the same socio-economic formation, which differ from each other in the degree of development of the economy and the maturity of social relations.

Socialism does not evolve on its own basis. Despite all of its enormous contributions to world history, socialism nevertheless carries many remnants of the previous (bourgeois, capitalist – V. V.) system, from which it evolved, in its economics, morals, legal system, and in the thoughts of its citizens. Communism is a more developed and advanced stage of social life, and it can only emerge after socialism has reached its full potential. All the negative effects of the capitalist system will be entirely eliminated under communism" (On the Program of the Communist Party... Report of the Comrade N.S. Khrushchev, 1962, p. 166).

In general, the development and introduction of "scientific communism" as a basic component of Soviet social theory and political doctrine can be associated with **M.S. Khrushchev**, and above all, an influential ideologist in the Politburo of the CPSU, **M.A. Suslov** (see, for example, Zhuravlev, 2020; Vikov, 2018), as well as with the initiatives of a new generation of philosophers, historians, and sociologists – future influential scientists and leaders of leading scientific academic institutes – **Yu.P. Frantseva**, **M.M. Rutkevych**, **O.M. Kovalov**, academicians and social scientists **P.M. Fedosieieva**, and **O.M. Rumiantseva**. In their minds, "*scientific communism*" would be comparable to "*socialist society change theories*" or "*sociological science*", but without sociological data but with a forecast of the near future. This, in their opinion, was what you needed to know about Soviet society in order to participate in its final transformation into a communist one. It is not for nothing that the third program of the party, adopted at the XXII Congress of the CPSU in 1961, finally gave a detailed definition of communism" (cited by Sechnev)⁹.

⁹ The definition of communism was first formally put forth in 1961 in the CPSU program at the state level. It read: "*Communism is a classless social system with a single national ownership of the means of production and full social equality of all members of society, where, together with the comprehensive development of people, productive forces will grow on the basis of constantly developing science and technology, all societal wealth-generating resources will be in full flow, and the principle "from everyone according to their ability, to every one according to their needs" will be achieved.*" "*Communism is a highly organized society of free and*

conscious workers, in which public self-government will be established, work for the benefit of society will be the first vital need for everyone, and as a conscious necessity, everyone's abilities will be used to the greatest benefit for the people" (Program of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 1965, p. 544).

Political science researchers and individuals who are not familiar with the history and postulates of the Soviet party doctrine should be aware that the most recent explanation made by the CPSU is contained in the "new edition" of the Party's program. It was adopted at the beginning of the "perestroika" period in the USSR

It is important to keep in mind that in the early 1960s, "the request for political science came in the Soviet Union from above," from individuals closely connected with political practice, in order to make an accurate assessment of the factors that led to the emergence of "scientific communism" as a subfield of social studies and a mandatory academic discipline" (the interests of members of the Presidium of the Central Committee of the CPSU, the ideas and beliefs of young scientists and initiative consultants of the Central Committee of the CPSU, and the outstanding political scientists of the future, for example, **R. Shakhnazarova** or **F. Burlatskyi**, who participated in the preparation of a new 1961 party program). And, first and foremost, it was "about global changes in the entire state's social and political life", and "this required science to justify the transformation" of the dictatorial, pro-cultural, totalitarian state" of the Stalin era "into a modern, civilized, and democratic" (Vorobyev 2004, p. 170).

As for the emergence and propaganda of the social and philosophical-political conception and the Communist Party ideologue/doctrine of "developed socialism" in the USSR, then, at first glance, an extract from an article in the Great Russian Encyclopedia (2004-2017) suffices to provide background information on their history and basic ideas about the process of "building communism in the Soviet Union" and about the importance of the preliminary phases of "developed socialism" for it, but already in the discourse of post-Soviet narratives.

So, a fragment of an article in the Great Russian Encyclopedia is sufficient for information reference about the history and basic ideas of the ideology or doctrine of "building communism in the Soviet Union" and the need for these preliminary "phases of developed socialism" – but already in the discourse of post-Soviet narratives. It says: "It was assumed that by 1980, the current generation of Soviet people would live under communism. "The construction of communism was associated with the solution of such tasks as the creation of its material and technical base, the achievement of higher, in comparison with the United States, production of goods per capita, the development of communist social relations, and the "education of a new person" based on the principles of the "moral code of the builder of communism", which did not contradict universal values. The concept of "developed socialism", which denoted a new extended stage in the development of the socialist phase and gave an indefinite delay for entering

the communist phase, was first introduced by the party's ideologists in the late 1960s in response to the obvious utopian nature of the communist project. "The construction of developed socialism in the USSR was proclaimed by General Secretary **L.I. Brezhnev** at the 24th Congress of the CPSU (1971), and this conclusion was enshrined in the Constitution of 1977, which also contained a description of this stage as a natural one on the way to communism" (The Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 2004-2017).

But, in our opinion, in order to clarify the information from the "Great Russian Encyclopedia" and to get a more correct understanding of the ideological and lexical specifics of the basic documents of the CPSU and the CPC, it is necessary to recall that the term or concept "developed socialism" was first used by the General Secretary of the Central Committee of the CPSU, **L.V. Brezhnev**, in the address to citizens on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the October Revolution in 1967. And in the Preamble of the Constitution of the USSR of 1977, it is already clearly written that "guided", among other things, by the "ideas of scientific communism," "a developed socialist society has been built in the USSR". At this stage, as socialism develops on its own, the creative forces of the new system and the advantages of the socialist way of life are increasingly revealed, and the workers are increasingly enjoying the fruits of the great revolutionary conquests. "It is a society in which powerful productive forces have been created, along with advanced science and culture, in which the welfare of the people is constantly growing and conditions are increasingly favorable for the comprehensive development of the individual." (Constitution (fundamental law) of the Union of Soviet..., 1977). A developed socialist society has been built in our country, according to the Ukrainian SSR's subsequently adopted Constitution from 1978. In its senses and meanings the new concept emphasized (in contrast to the previous and so-called Stalin's Constitution of 1936, which stated that socialism was built "mostly" in the USSR since the "foundations of socialism" were created) that by the mid-1970s, socialism in the Soviet Union had acquired an almost perfect form (colloquially, it became "full socialism"). But competent Soviet scientists did not limit themselves to the idea of "developed socialism." Distancing themselves from the party's ideological clichés, they replaced them in their works with a more neutral one, in particular, "mature socialism" (Soviet Constitution and Myths of Sovietologists, 1981, pp. 16, 44, 71). And yet another crucial

by the XXVII Congress in 1986; it proclaimed the following in an optimistically utopian and abstractly-humanistic way: "Communism is a classless social system with a single national ownership of the means of production, full social equality of all members of society, where, together with the comprehensive development of people, productive forces will grow on the basis of constantly developing science and technology, all societal wealth-generating resources will be in full flow, and the principle "from everyone according to their ability, to everyone – according to their needs" will be achieved. "Communism is a highly organized society of free and conscious workers, in which public self-government will be established, work for the benefit of society will be the first vital need

for everyone, and as a conscious necessity, everyone's abilities will be used to the greatest benefit for the people" (Materials of the 27th Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, 1986, p. 138).

As a result, when compared to the 1961 definition, the "new" (1986) redaction of the CPSU program actually maintained the same definition of the key components of communism. A new feature was added to the definition of communist society: "public self-government will be established," and instead of the wording: "using the abilities of each with the greatest fullness for the people", a similar paraphrase of their social application was proposed: "with the greatest benefit".

theoretical socio-philosophical, political-ideological moment for contrasting Soviet and contemporary Chinese party doctrines, as well as strategic socio-political recommendations or prescriptions. Its essence lies in the fact that **L.I. Brezhnev** stated in the 1981 Report of the Central Committee of the CPSU that "during this time, extensive experience of socialist and communist construction in the USSR has been accumulated. This experience indisputably proves that our movement towards communism is carried out through the stage of a developed socialist society. This is ... a necessary, natural, and historically long period in the creation of the Communist formation") (XXVI Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union... 1981, p. 97).

Concerning the interpretation of the essence and role of *developed socialism as a new*, previously unpredicted by Marxists of the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth centuries¹⁰, *special stage in the process of building a communist society*, Chinese Marxist researchers and politicians, as well as the political leadership in the USSR since the post-Khrushchev era, recognized its absolute necessity, that is, they stated that there should be a kind of transition stage/period of development of the socialist system between the stage of socialism and communism, namely the *stage of developed socialism*. And in our opinion, there is no significant, theoretical, fundamental semantic difference between the concepts and terms "*developed socialism*" and "*high degree of development of a socialist society*". The difference in the names of the intermediate, transitional period from the stage of "socialism built primarily" before the stage of "communism," which manifested itself in modern varieties of Marxism, that is, between Soviet Marxism-Leninism and Sinicized Marxism, can be considered purely stylistic.

It should also be noted that there is one fundamental political-ideological and even mental difference between the USSR and the PRC, between the leadership of the CPSU and the CPC: Chinese theorists, ideologists, state and party leaders (taking into account not only the problematic and sad experience of the history of the Soviet Union but also the methods and consequences of the aggressive policy of the "Great Proletarian Cultural Revolution" conducted by **Mao Zedong** and his poorly educated adherents from 1966 to 1976) traditionally do not make loud statements about the imminent victory of communism (as **M.S. Khrushchev** did and other party officials and propagandists continued to follow his example for a number of years). Since the end of the "Mao era", the Chinese Communist Par-

ty's leadership has refrained from making radical statements or openly voluntary decisions with the intention of artificially accelerating and stimulating the actualization of their strategic objective and the officially declared ideal – building communism in China. *And what is particularly important is that the tasks and goals of the Chinese Communist Party outlined in the Constitution actually deny the possibility of reaching the phase of communism in a very short period.*

It is not just a defining characteristic of Chinese political culture to operate symbols, withhold specifics of their grand plans in detail, or the country's progress in terms of socioeconomic indicators, which would be undeniable proof that their large-scale projects have been carried out. Similarly, this does not demonstrate the inability of Chinese Marxists – theorists and politicians – to predict and plan for the future of Chinese society scientifically and strategically. In this case, the absence of time markers in the CPC's program documents or public instructions or statements of its leaders about specific dates for the completion of certain stages of socialist and communist construction in the PRC primarily indicates that they recognize that the *revolutionary socioeconomic, technical, technological, spiritual, and cultural China's leap* (of this complex organized society, politics, multi-ethnic national community, unique and self-sufficient cultural and civilizational type, moreover, in the conditions of the global transformation of the existing world order) *from socialism to communism is impossible and unacceptable*. On the contrary, all members of the Chinese political class and scientific community are convinced adherents of the theoretical approach, which axiomatically postulates (in fact, it does not require any proof) that the process of communist construction, firstly, will be very long in time, and secondly, in the type and way of its progressive development, it can only be evolutionary.

Conclusion

So, for a scientific analysis of the genesis of Marxism (both Soviet, that is, Russified, and Chinese, or Sinicized), as well as an adequate understanding and evaluation of the program documents and practice of activity of the leading Marxist parties in the history of the twentieth century (primarily, the CPSU and the CPC), it is possible to proceed from the assumption that in such conditions, that is, in a situation of active reform of economic and political relations (during the "Khrushchev Thaw" and then "Gorbachev Perestroika", and on the other hand, fundamental socio-economic and political-ideological modernization in the

¹⁰ It is important to note that Marx's Communist conception-ideologeme, particularly its axiomatics, served as the ideological basis for Soviet Marxism's social, political-philosophical, and political-economic theories as well as the core of the Soviet Union's state political ideology. Up to the end of the 1950s, it received number of significant additions from Soviet social scientists and ideologues of the VKP(b) – CPSU (corrections, details, arguments aplenty, etc.). Furthermore, the state-political power and numerous institutions of the massive party management apparatus actively and purposefully sought and attempted to implement in practice the "socialist-communist project" (which did not imply

any stage of developed socialism) in the Soviet Union using all available possibilities, political-ideological means, and resources, both inside and outside the USSR (for many decades after the revolution of 1917). The Soviet social theorists and Communist Party ideologists did not revise the traditional Marxist two-phase model of the evolution of the Communist socio-economic formation until the second half of the twentieth century, during the so-called "Brezhnev era", adding a third phase – *developed socialism*. It was precisely this stage that began to be understood and interpreted as a special and necessary stage on the path from socialism to communism.

PRC since the late 1970s, including radical transformations of the foreign policy strategy of its leadership) due to the urgent need to correct the Marxist-Leninist doctrines of the communist parties ruling in them and reorient the ideological values of the masses from narrow-class to general-democratic (although extremely abstract), in the intellectual environment of socialist-type societies (despite the differences in their political and spiritual culture, traditions, value preferences, and mentality) *similar system requests were formed*.

For the most part, such research activities in modern China focused on the preparation and implementation of projects in the form or under the slogan "de-Stalinization of Marxism", that is, the modernization of the version of Marxist teaching that by the middle of the twentieth century had become orthodox and scholastic, and in the political system and in the state ideology of the countries of socialism (regardless of their level of development), as well as in the mass consciousness of their people, performed the functions of metanarrative.

It is also worth emphasizing that the *system request to modernize Marxism*, or at least adapt its basic philosophical and socio-political postulates, scientific and socio-political functions to modern realities (which were fundamentally different from those in Europe at the end of the nineteenth and beginning of the twentieth centuries, in the USSR in the 1920s and first half of the twentieth century, and in China in the 1950s and 1970s), naturally updated the entire range of issues directly related to the interpretation of the essence and role of Marxist-Leninist philosophical and socio-political teaching in general, as well as to the peculiarities of its most influential political-ideological and socio-economic varieties, namely, the political doctrines and strategic programs of the socialist and communist construction of the CPSU and the CPC.

The fact that **Stalin's** model of Marxist-Leninist political theory and philosophy evolved into a metanarrative under the circumstances of the PRC's early socialism and nation-state construction illustrates the peculiar political history of China over the past century.

Therefore, in the process of implementing the socio-economic and political strategy of the CPC, focused in the early 1980s already on the principles of a market (its temporary name: capitalist, bourgeois) economy and a liberalized system of political representation (that is, at the stage of practical implementation of its own "market socialism" construction project, dubbed "*socialism with Chinese characteristics*", which provided for the stimulation of large private property development and the openness of China's economy and foreign policy to the Western world with its values), Chinese Marxist theorists and party ideologists of the CPC quite naturally faced the challenge of modernizing of Marxist-Leninist teaching (see, for example, Zhang Shuhua; Vilkov, 2022, pp. 70-83) and socio-political doctrine. It essentially came down to the fact that it was impossible to abandon Marx's theory for political and ideological reasons. In the meantime, Stalin's version was wholly out of date, and the Soviet rendition was inappropriate. They were purely orthodox, largely false, and could neither conceptually explain and justify the specifics of

Chinese (Sinicized) Marxism nor ideologically legitimize the CCP's goals and objectives of fundamental, non-standard, radically innovative (including Marxist theory) for the world political history of socialist transformations in China in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries.

Meanwhile, the idea about the uniqueness of *Chinese Marxism*, which has been conceptually and terminologically formulated and characterized in the CPC's program, statutory documents, and the People's Republic of China's Constitution and is conceptually defined and interpreted as "*Sinicized Marxism*" in the works of modern Chinese philosophers and social scientists, has once again actualized a long-standing but fundamental problem for Marxist theoretical thought. Its essence (in ideological, theoretical-methodological, and ideological-political aspects) lies in the fact that the very justification of the concept of "*Sinicized Marxism*" ("*adaptation of Marxism to the Chinese context*") actually denies the possibility and necessity of the existence and development of Marxist teaching as a universal general and socio-philosophical theory, as well as revolutionary, political, and socio-economic conceptions (respectively, party-political doctrine).

From a theoretical and methodological standpoint, this happens because in developing and justifying the possibility of the existence of Marxism in world history only in its *specific* or *nationally peculiar* forms (which are classified and referred to as *Sinicized*, *Russified*, etc. Marxism), theoreticians, philosophers, and ideologues absolutize national specificity in the process of development of Marxism. Only in light of the specific historical circumstances of social life do they recognize the theoretical and ideological value of modernizing or adapting Marxist axiomatics. In this case, philosophers and political figures commonly (which has already happened many times in different eras) understand and interpret of Marxist theory as a practical, purely instrumental adaptation of Marxism to national specifics, the unique objective-historical logic and tasks of socialist revolutions, national and state construction in each individual country, and the goals and methods of implementing socialist socioeconomic, political, and cultural transformations in them (see, for example, publications by Li Junju, Zhang Shuhua).

However, this approach *stimulates the absolutization of the specific historical uniqueness of Marxist* manifestations in theoretical, methodological, and political-ideological terms. It becomes an ideological-theoretical and political-ideological platform for the recognition and apology of the general and political-philosophical model, which requires acknowledging that *Marxist* teaching can only be the sum of its self-sufficient national or nationalized by theorists and ideologists forms, coexisting in history under the universal, revolutionary, progressive, and still appealing (for many large communities and social groups) name of "*Marxism*".

Although, as history has repeatedly shown, the aforementioned "modernization" (as "*nationalization*") of Marxist teachings can serve as an ideological-theoretical and methodological foundation for philosophical and ideological revisionism as well as a trigger and

motive for political or military conflict between states led by communist parties.

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